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TOWARDS THE MODERN THEORY OF GEOGRAPHY: GEOGRAPHICAL LAWS AND THEIR SIGNIFICANCE

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Abstract. The geographic laws examined should be regarded as the leading ones for the current stage of development of geographical science. The discipline's provision with factual material, methods of qualitative and quantitative research, and the use of new technical tools allows for the continued advancement of physical geography theory in the future. The discovery of the presented geographic laws, as well as their interpretation and application in the interests of rational (optimal) environmental management, has become possible precisely now, at the present stage, owing to the active and prioritized implementation of the system-dynamic paradigm. The spatial-territorial paradigm continues to be applied when necessary, non-prioritarily, in relevant cases and natural conditions.

გეოგრაფიის თანამედროვე თეორიისკენ: გეოგრაფიული კანონები და მათი მნიშვნელობა

იუ. დ. შუისკი

გეოგრაფიის მეცნიერებათა დოქტორი, პროფესორი, ფიზიკური გეოგრაფიის, გარემოს მართვისა და გეოგრაფიული სისტემების ტექნოლოგიების დეპარტამენტი

შამპანსკის შესახვევი, 2, გეოლოგიისა და გეოგრაფიის ფაკულტეტი, ოდესა ი.ი.

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აბსტრაქტი. განხილული გეოგრაფიული კანონები გეოგრაფიული მეცნიერების განვითარების ამჟამინდელი ეტაპისთვის წამყვან კანონებად უნდა ჩაითვალოს. დისციპლინის ფაქტობრივი მასალით, თვისებრივი და რაოდენობრივი კვლევის მეთოდებით უზრუნველყოფა და ახალი ტექნიკური ინსტრუმენტების გამოყენება მომავალში ფიზიკური გეოგრაფიის თეორიის განვითარების გაგრძელების საშუალებას იძლევა. წარმოდგენილი გეოგრაფიული კანონების აღმოჩენა, ასევე მათი ინტერპრეტაცია და გამოყენება რაციონალური (ოპტიმალური) გარემოს მართვის ინტერესებიდან გამომდინარე, შესაძლებელი გახდა სწორედ ახლა, ამჟამინდელ ეტაპზე, სისტემურ-დინამიური პარადიგმის აქტიური და პრიორიტეტული განხორციელების წყალობით. სივრცულ-ტერიტორიული პარადიგმა კვლავ გამოიყენება საჭიროების შემთხვევაში, არაპრიორიტეტულად, შესაბამის შემთხვევებში და ბუნებრივ პირობებში.

Definition of Geography. According to the theoretical works of S.V. Rudnytskyi, A.O. Grygoryev, M.M. Yermolaev, K.I. Herenchuk, D.L. Armand, O.M. Marynych, P.H. Shyshchenko, V.M. Pashchenko, and other scholars, geography is a fundamental science that has accumulated

knowledge over many centuries. From its earliest stages, geography described, investigated, and evaluated the environment in which humans live - referred to as **γῆ** (Earth, environment) - and, over time, the descriptive research (**γραφῶ**) of the known part of the planet was also associated with **γῆ**. Hence, the scientific and philosophical discipline received the name **γεῖγραφο** - *geography*, or «description of the Earth»

As a result, the modern understanding of geography has incorporated the view that the *object of geographical research is the highly complex environment inhabited by humans*. Humans consume natural resources, engage in anthropogenic activities, and strive to organize rational environmental management. This environment on the Earth's surface has received the appropriately precise name *geographical envelope*. According to contemporary geographical encyclopedias of various countries and years of publication, it represents one of the most complex predominantly exogenous natural systems, which has undergone profound differentiation throughout its existence [7, 8].

It has formed distinct geospheres, objects and their elements, natural components, and has integrated a wide range of active factors. Within it, continents, islands, oceans, and seas have developed together with water masses, seabeds, and living organisms. All of these components interact and interpenetrate intensively, leading to further complexities. Consequently, a unified theory of geography emerged - one fundamentally different from the theories of mathematics, medicine, economics, military science, and similar disciplines.

Over the centuries, qualitative and quantitative geographic descriptions and measurements, both direct and remote, as well as their cartographic representation, made it necessary to develop “subsidiary” (sectoral and interdisciplinary) geographical sciences within the unified body of geography [3]. The solid envelope came to be studied in detail by geology and mining sciences; the pedosphere - by soil science; relief forms - by geomorphology; the atmosphere - by climatology, meteorology, and synoptics; waters - by oceanology, hydrology, and hydrogeology. Plants and animals are studied by general biogeography, including geobotany and zoogeography. Specific objects, forces, phenomena, and mechanisms within the geographic envelope are investigated by geochemistry, limnology, glaciology, volcanology, etc.

As a result, *partial theories* of individual geographical sciences have emerged and developed. These differ from the more comprehensive and *universal general theory of geography*, and cannot substitute for it in substantiating territorial organization, natural resource use, or environmental management as a whole. Thus, the essence of geography lies in the *qualitative, quantitative, evaluative, and cartographic study of the global system of the geographical envelope*, with all its complexity, hierarchy, primary and secondary information flows, and practical relevance.

The modern definition of the concept «*geography*» was substantiated in the works of Yu.D. Shuisky [5, 10] as follows: Geography is an ancient, multifaceted synthetic science, oriented toward world perception and resource studies, which investigates the objects, factors, processes, and mechanisms of formation of natural systems at various levels of organization within the geographical envelope and its geospheres, involving the anthropogenic factor and considering their spatial distribution. To this day, geography studies the properties and spatial arrangement of geospheres, elements, components, and structural parts of the geographical envelope to organize the harmonious (rational) use of natural resources, ensure their conservation, and support comfortable living conditions for humans and society as a whole.

During the development of scientific geography, the need gradually emerged to reveal and formulate certain geographical laws. Until several decades ago, leading geographers of the highest qualification argued that geography possessed only two laws - the *law of latitudinal geographical*

zonality and the *law of altitudinal geographical beltiness*, as proposed by A.O. Grygoryev, M.M. Yermolaev, K.I. Herenchuk, A.H. Isachenko, P.H. Shyshchenko, and others. However, the massive and increasingly diverse influx of geographical information has clearly demonstrated that *geography exhibits necessary, essential, and stable relationships between natural phenomena and physical-geographical processes, often on a global scale* [1, 4, 6, 7, 8].

At the same time, anthropogenic pressures on the environment have sharply intensified, and significant changes of both exogenous and endogenous nature have become evident. This has created favorable conditions for identifying and analyzing the most important geographical laws [9, 10].

Sectors of the Geographical Envelope.

As is known [1, 7, 8], a significant proportion of geographical researchers rely on the conceptual analogy between the «*geographical envelope*» and the «*landscape envelope*». At the same time, nearly all geographers emphasize that “landscapes exist everywhere” and are terrigenous systems. However, this approach must be challenged, since fundamental research conducted in the second half of the 20th century fully revealed the specific features of natural systems in the ocean, on the seafloor, in the coastal zone, in the atmosphere, and within the biospheric envelope — all of which differ fundamentally from landscapes [4, 8, 9, 11].

In his works, M.D. Hrodzynskiy [2, p.16] conclusively defined geographical landscapes as *terrigenous systems* based on five principal characteristics, which categorically cannot be applied to the description of oceanic (thalassogenic) and coastal-marine (aquascape) global systems (“sectors”). Thus, landscapes cannot form an envelope in the scientifically adapted sense of the term, because an envelope must completely encompass a given object.

Accordingly, we arrived at a well-grounded conclusion regarding the identification of *three principal exogenous sectors* within the geographical envelope, which serve as environments within which humans use natural resources. All of them are studied by *17 sectoral and 13 interdisciplinary geographical sciences*, in accordance with the dimensions and structure of the geographical envelope [5, p.15]. Each of these sciences investigates a particular object, element, component, or factor of the geographical envelope as part of the aforementioned three sectors, necessarily within the framework of the general theory of geography.

Within each sector, we constructed *hierarchical series of systems*, ranging from elementary to global ones. This made it possible to develop and present an integral theoretical correlational scheme of the geographical envelope for the following sectors:

- a) *landscape (terrigenous)*;
- b) *coastal-marine (aquascape)*;
- c) *oceanic (thalassogenic)* [7, p.45].

All these sectors may evolve toward more advanced and efficient states in the interest of optimal environmental management, with the application of certain geographical laws developed with the participation and methodology of general scientific laws that are significant for geography and influence its general theory.

Formulation and Application of Geographical Laws.

Throughout the development of geography, general scientific principles and requirements for the laws of nature and society have been employed in scientific works by numerous philosophers and scholars of science - proponents of the dialectics of nature. Among them are D.I. Mendeleev, V.V. Dokuchaev, M.M. Yermolaev, P.K. Bozhych, B.M. Kedrov, I.V. Krut, O.M. Marynych, K.I. Herenchuk, V.M. Ptashchenko, and others [9].

The *first attempt* to identify, formulate, and apply several such laws was made using the example of the highly dynamic coastal-marine global system in the major monograph by Yurii Shuisky, “*History of Development and Methodology of Shore Studies*” (2018). Within such systems, the consequences of natural and anthropogenic processes manifest very rapidly - one to three orders of magnitude faster than in typical landscape systems. Thus, it became possible to verify the consequences of various anthropogenic impacts across different geo-environments of different sectors. This material has served as the initial foundation for refining the definitions provided in the monograph. Further developments were applied in numerous general-geographical works by the author [5–11], published both in Ukraine and abroad.

From the author’s publications, the most important achievement is the identification of the *structure of geographical laws and their probable significance*. Their great theoretical value has now become fully evident. We believe that, at the present stage, it is appropriate to list the most important *partial geographical laws*.

Traditionally, among partial («random – isolated») geographical laws, all referenced geographers identify the *retrospective law*, the oldest one, known since the works of Eudoxus and Aristotle. Over many centuries, it has undergone gradual development and has become one of the most significant laws in paleogeography and other sectoral sciences. The recommendations of D.P. Horskyi, M.M. Yermolaev, V.V. Orlenko, K.I. Herenchuk, O.M. Marynych, M.F. Veklich, and V.P. Paliienko have been particularly influential.

Thus, the essence of this law is as follows:

the inherent, essential, and stable interconnections among geographical factors, processes, phenomena, and natural mechanisms within the geographical envelope determine the gradual, ordered transformations of natural systems of various levels of organization within the hierarchical series of planetary exogenous sectors.

In the works of F.F. Bellingshausen, W.M. Davis, F. von Richthofen, V.V. Dokuchaev, A. Hettner, A.O. Hryhoriev, H.I. Tanfiliev, H.I. Denysyk, and many others — both national and international geographers — considerable attention has been devoted to the law of latitudinal geographical zonation. Some scholars asserted that geography possesses only this single law; among them were O.M. Smirnov, Ya.S. Edelshtein, N.A. Hvozdetzkyi, D.L. Armand, and K.Ye. Povitiana.

In recent years, we have identified and analyzed the following interpretation of this law [9]:

Within the geographical envelope, a unique form of territorial differentiation has emerged and continues to develop; namely, all exogenous geographical factors, components, and natural geographical systems undergo regular latitudinal transformations from the equator toward the poles. This general form manifests itself through the localization of specific natural («zonal») complexes, depending on the latitudinal distribution of solar radiation and the response of the underlying surface to this distribution.

Some authors consider the «*law of altitudinal beltiness*» to be a separate geographical law. According to this law, somewhat analogous to the previous one, *altitudinal natural systems may change with elevation, transitioning from equatorial to polar types of various levels of organization (from elementary systems to megasystems).*

In the 1990s, the author proposed the definition, analysis, meaning, and theoretical significance of the «*law of geographical locality*» [9].

It may be correlated with the concept of *regional studies* in socio-economic (human) geography, though this requires additional theoretical development.

The law is formulated as follows:

«Within the various planetary sectors and geospheres of the geographical envelope, throughout the course of evolution and geographical differentiation, a multitude of geographical systems of different hierarchical levels has emerged; each of these systems is unique and original in space and time with respect to quantity, form, internal structure, state, dynamics, properties, combinations, and the relationships of location, factors, elements, and components».

This necessitates an individualized approach to distinct systems of different levels of organization and different hierarchical series within each sector of the geographical envelope, especially in connection with environmental and resource use.

The Law of Rhythmic Dynamics

The *law of rhythmic dynamics* was first presented as a scientific report at the 3rd International Scientific and Practical Online Conference dedicated to the memory of the renowned Soviet geographer, Head of the Department of Physical Geography at Odesa I.I. Mechnikov National University, Professor S.T. Bielozorov.

This law was elaborated, analyzed, its groups of variants were identified, and its graphical trends were demonstrated for different types of natural resource use across the three sectors of the geographical envelope.

As a result, we formulate it as follows:

The evolutionary long-term catastrophic - evolutionary development of a geographical system is described by an exponential curve of various types, composed of secondary subordinate exponential oscillations of lower hierarchical levels, down to elementary initial ones.

The essence of this geographical law is particularly important in connection with the substantial intensification of anthropogenic excitation affecting systems of various hierarchical levels in different environments.

Conclusions.

The geographic laws examined should be regarded as the leading ones for the current stage of development of geographical science. The discipline's provision with factual material, methods of qualitative and quantitative research, and the use of new technical tools allows for the continued advancement of physical geography theory in the future. The discovery of the presented geographic laws, as well as their interpretation and application in the interests of rational (optimal) environmental management, has become possible precisely now, at the present stage, owing to the active and prioritized implementation of the system-dynamic paradigm. The spatial-territorial paradigm continues to be applied when necessary, non-prioritarily, in relevant cases and natural conditions.

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